

Effect of Brain-Based Learning Strategies on Educational Aspiration of Students at Upper Primary Level

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Abstract

The presented research study is related to the study of the effect of brain-based learning strategies used by teachers on the educational aspirations of students. The main objective was to examine the effect of brain-based learning strategies on the educational aspirations of students. The researcher used a quasi-experimental research method for the research. The researcher selected P.V Girls Intermediate College (Dormitory school) governed by Dayalbagh Educational Institute by purposive sample selection method and intact sampling method was used for the selection of class 7, sections A and B. The number of students in both groups (section A experimental and Section B control group) was equal 50-50. After conducting a pre-test using the Level of Educational Aspiration Test developed by Dr. Yasmin Ghani Khan to evaluate the academic aspirations of students in both experimental and control groups, the researcher taught science using 15 lesson plans based on brain-based learning strategies to the experimental group. Meanwhile, in the control group, the same subject matter was taught by using traditional teaching methods. Afterward, a post-test of the educational aspirations of students was conducted by the researcher. In the context of students' educational aspirations, statistical analysis was performed on the obtained pre-test and post-test scores. Using the pre-test and post-test scores obtained in the context of students' academic aspirations, statistical tests such as the Mann-Whitney U-value and Wilcoxon Sign Rank Test were used to examine the significance of brain-based learning strategies. Based on the results of the present research study, it was found that the use of brain-based learning strategies in teaching has a significant impact on students' educational aspirations. Therefore, the hypothesis made in the context "There is no significant effect of Brain-Based Learning Strategies and conventional methods on the Educational Aspiration of students at upper primary level in experimental and control group after treatment." has been rejected. Based on the results of this research, it can be said that teachers should use brain-based learning strategies in their teaching-learning activities, so that students' educational aspirations can be raised to a higher level, and they can also express their proficiencies in the context of various aspects of education.

Introduction of the Study

Each country's education system has distinct goals and objectives tailored to its unique circumstances and requirements. These aims typically center around modifying learners' behavior and nurturing skill sets through the learning process. Learning, at its core, represents the primary objective of any educational undertaking, facilitated through a range of teaching and learning methodologies. As the great Albert Einstein once remarked on **Education**:

“I never teach my pupils. I only attempt to provide the conditions in which they learn”.

Based on this statement, it is evident that teachers can only provide conditions and circumstances to students, as each student's learning ability is different. These differences are due to the varying abilities of the human brain, which is a superior and complex organ that allows humans to generate new ideas and concepts in unique ways. Scientists have conducted studies to understand the human brain better, revealing its ability to perform multiple activities simultaneously and store identical information in various lobes of the brain. When teaching strategies are based on an understanding of how the brain functions, learning becomes more effective and meaningful for students. Jensen (2008)

conducted research on "Brain-Based Learning," which focuses on teaching strategies and principles that align with the brain's functioning. According to Hasra (2007), learning becomes more meaningful and permanent when using brain-based learning techniques. Kaur (2013) also researched the most effective teaching strategies to encourage students and help educators achieve their goals more effectively.

Brain-based learning is a child-centered approach that aims to enhance various aspects of student learning such as achievement, knowledge acquisition, retention, performance, mental and emotional health, interest in learning, attention, concentration, and attitude toward learning. This approach recognizes that all these learning activities depend on the structure, functions, and cognitive processes of the human brain. Brain-based learning emphasizes that all teaching and learning processes should be based on the cognitive activities of the brain. By aligning teaching and learning with the workings of the brain, there is a possibility of achieving higher quality and effective teaching that has a positive impact on various psychological factors of the student.

It is important to recognize that all students learn differently based on factors such as their age, growth, developmental stage, maturation rate, developmental tasks, intelligence, interests, attitudes, abilities, aptitude, aspirations, thinking patterns, environmental conditions, and more. Therefore, teaching approaches, strategies, models, methods, techniques, and aids should be tailored to suit each student's unique needs and abilities.

Researchers have provided evidence that Brain-based learning is highly beneficial in enhancing various aspects of student learning, such as increasing interest, attention power, knowledge acquisition, retention, confidence, academic achievement, performance in various activities, transfer of learning, application ability, and active participation in teaching-learning activities. This approach can enhance students' educational aspirations. According to the English Dictionary (1968), the "level of aspiration" can be defined as "The standard by which failure or as being up to what he expects of himself. Educational aspiration is critical as it encourages and energizes individuals to engage in educational activities. As Sherwood (1998) states, all types of aspirations motivate individuals to achieve better results. Every person has unique aspirations, but educational and vocational aspirations are especially important for students, as they can influence their behavior and activities during their educational period. The level of educational aspiration of an individual is a crucial motivating factor for their higher education.

As per Cao and Thompson (2003), aspiration refers to an individual's personal desire to achieve their objectives or goals in a specific occupation or level of education. This aspiration for education and vocation helps individuals to adopt goal-oriented behavior, which motivates them to strive for excellence. Consequently, students experience an increase in cognitive, emotional, and psychomotor activities, resulting in the formation of new neural pathways and an increase in the number of neurons in the brain. According to Fischbach (1999), the composition of neural networks and synapses plays a crucial role in learning. As a result, students become more adept at logical thinking, decision-making, problem-solving, and understanding even in challenging situations.

In the present study, the researcher aims to investigate how brain-based learning strategies effect students' educational aspirations. By exploring this connection, teachers can incorporate brain-based learning strategies into their teaching-learning process, which can help teachers for playing a pivotal role in enhancing the educational aspirations

of students. The findings of this research will be beneficial for various stakeholders in the education system, including educational agencies, policymakers, educational authorities, teachers, students, parents, and others, by providing insights for effective and meaningful teaching and learning.

2. Statement of the Problem

A Study on the Effect of Brain-Based Learning Strategies on Educational Aspiration of Students at Upper Primary Level.

3. Objectives of the Study

1. To develop teaching-learning material on the base of Brain-Based Learning strategies for science subject at the upper primary level.
2. To compare the Educational Aspiration of students at the upper primary level in the experimental and control group before treatment.
3. To compare the Educational Aspiration of students at the upper primary level in the experimental and control group after treatment.
4. To study the effect of Brain-based Learning Strategies and conventional method on the Educational Aspiration of students at upper primary level in the experimental and control group.

4. Hypothesis of the Study

1. There is no significant difference between Educational Aspiration of students at upper primary level in the experimental & control group before treatment.
2. There is no significant difference between Educational Aspiration of students at upper primary level in the experimental & control group after treatment.
3. There is no significant effect of Brain-Based Learning Strategies and conventional methods on the Educational Aspiration of students at upper primary level in experimental and control group after treatment.

5. Delimitations of the study

The present research was conducted under the following delimitations –

1. The study was delimited to Agra City only.
2. The study was confined to P.V. Girls Intermediate College (Dormetry school) governed by Dayalbagh Educational Institute.
3. The study was conducted on 7th-class students.
4. The study was delimited to science subject only.

6. Variables of the Study

The researcher selected the following variables for the present study –

Figure 1 Variables of the study

7. Research Methodology

The Research Methodology of any study depends upon the aim of the research. The aim of the present study is to develop teaching-learning material on the base of Brain-Based Learning strategies for (science subject) upper primary students and check out its effectiveness for educational aspiration and logical thinking among them. A Pretest-Posttest Non-Equivalent Control Group design of quantitative Quasi-Experimental Design had been chosen by the researcher for the achievement of the objectives of the present study. But in order to develop a more in-

depth understanding of how the Pedagogical Instructional strategies of Brain-based learning worked, the researcher used Mixed Method Design which involves the usage of both the Quantitative as well as Qualitative approaches. The details of the research methodology adopted for achieving the objectives of the present research work had discussed under the following heads i.e., Research Method, Sampling method, Tools, and Statistical Techniques. The research design followed in this study has been presented briefly in the following figure:

Figure 2 Research Methodology

8. Research Process

The Pretest-Posttest Non-Equivalent Control Group design was selected for the achievement of the

objective of present study. The complete details have been given in the following table:

Table 1 Research Process of the study

S. No.	Groups	Sample Size	Pre-Treatment Phase (Pre-Test)	Implementation/ Treatment Phase	Post-Treatment Phase (Post-Test)
1.	Experimental Group	50	Level of Educational Aspiration Test	Brain-Based Learning Strategies were used for the teaching of science subject.	Level of Educational Aspiration Test
2.	Control Group	50		Conventional Teaching Methods were used for teaching of science subject.	

9. Sample of the study

The population for the present study was the students of class 7th or age group approximately 13-14 years. The researcher used the Convenience sampling method of the Non-probability sampling method for the selection of school. Therefore Prem Vidyalaya, Dayalbagh Educational Institute, Agra was selected for the present study. After that student

of Class 7th had selected by the Intact sampling method. The researcher had decided section A of class 7th as the experimental group and section B as the control group for the quasi-experiment research. 50-50 students were enrolled in both sections. Therefore, total of 100 students were selected as the sample of the study.

Figure 3. Sample of the study

10. Research Tools of the Study

In this study, the researcher utilized the following research tools:

Teaching-Learning Material through Brain-Based Learning -

The researcher developed 15 lesson plans using brain-based learning strategies for teaching science at the upper primary level. These plans were administered to the experimental group, and every

activity in the teaching-learning process was based on the brain-based learning strategies prescribed for the 7th-grade science curriculum by the U.P Board.

Educational Aspiration Scale -

The Level of Educational Aspiration Test, developed by Dr. Yasmin Ghani Khan, was utilized in this study to assess the educational aspirations of the students.

11. Analysis and interpretation

Obj 1. To develop teaching-learning material on the base of Brain-Based Learning strategies for science subject at the upper primary level.

In the context of the present research, the researcher has developed 15 lesson plans for teaching science to seventh-grade students using brain-based learning strategies and principles. These lesson plans include various teaching methods, techniques, and activities designed to enhance learning and engagement, and incorporate different types of teaching aids to support the students' understanding. The researcher then implemented these lesson plans in the experimental group, using the brain-based learning strategies and activities outlined in Table 2. It will have interested to see, how these strategies have effective to improving students' educational aspiration by comparing the post test scores of the experimental group (who received the brain-based learning treatment) with the control group (who did not receive the treatment). After the treatment and analysis, this research can be able to determine, whether the brain-based learning strategies and principles were effect to improving students' various aspects of educational aspiration

(Family support, pupil's view, pupil's effort, and reality of aspired goal). The use of different teaching aids and activities regarding with brain-based learning strategies can also help to keep students engaged and motivated, which may further enhance their learning outcomes which are directly and indirectly related with their educational aspiration.

All the teaching methods, techniques, activities, and teaching aids mentioned in the above table are extremely helpful for teachers in designing their teaching based on brain-based learning strategies and making it effective. All these methods make the subject matter easy, understandable, and practical for the students, while also encouraging their participation in these activities. This helps the students to easily accomplish their learning while remaining active throughout the class. These methods are based on the neurosciences of the student's brain, which help to increase the number of neurons in students and make them highly active. As a result, students' cognitive activity increases when they perform these activities, and they can easily comprehend the subject matter in their minds, contributing significantly to the use of the subject matter in the future.

Table-2. Brain-based learning strategies

Teaching Methods	Teaching Techniques	Teaching Activities	Teaching Aids
5 E method	Concept mapping (Flow chart)	Graphic organizer	Flash Cards
Experiential Learning	Mind Mapping	Group discussion	Charts & Posters
Deductive & Inductive method	Graphic organizer	Case-based learning	Working & non-working Models
Gamification method	Reciprocal teaching	Reflective Writing	AI Apps
KWL	Role Play	Music/ Rhythm/Rhyme	Puppets
4 MAT	Semantic Maps	Drawing/Artwork Metaphoric Activities	Videos
Thematic Instruction	Tabulation for comparison	Visual Mapmaking	Visual Maps
Expository learning	Mnemonic devices	Learning Transformation	
Project-based learning	Visualization/Guided	Meditation	
Real-life dilemma	Analogies	Correlation with various subjects	
Cooperative learning	Exhibition	Healthy competitions	
Advance organizers	Field visit/excursion	Motivational Activities	
Collaborative learning	Brain Storming		
Problem-solving method	Formulas		
Demonstration	Question-answering		
Dramatization	Metacognition Techniques		
SQ3R	Involvement of feeling in teaching-learning		

Obj 2. To compare the Educational Aspiration of students at the upper primary level in the experimental and control group before treatment.

It seems like the researcher has collected data on the educational aspirations of the students before treatment in both the experimental and control groups of upper primary-level students. The data is presented in Table 3 and includes mean, median, and standard deviation values for each

group. This information can be used to compare the baseline educational aspirations of the two groups and ensure that they are similar before the treatment is applied. This is important because any differences in educational aspirations between the two groups could affect the outcomes of the study. By analysing the data, the researcher can determine if the two groups are comparable and make adjustments if necessary.

Table -3. Pre-test scores of Educational Aspiration’s mean, median, and standard deviation of students at the upper primary level in the experimental and control group

Groups	N	Mean	Median	Standard Deviation
Experimental	50	37.44	36	5.39
Control	50	37.68	37	4.27

As is seen in the above table, it appears that the educational aspirations of the students in both the experimental and control groups were found to be average realistic, with similar median values and standard deviations that deviate similarly from the mean. However, to confirm that the two groups are indeed similar in terms of educational aspirations,

the researcher has applied the Mann-Whitney U-test to the values of both groups. The results of this test had helped to determine whether there were any significant differences between the two groups that could affect the outcomes of the study. The values obtained from the test are presented in a separate following table of the research report.

Table - 4. Ranks of Educational Aspiration in experimental and control groups before treatment

Groups	N	Mean rank	Sum of Ranks
Experimental	50	48.36	2418
Control	50	52.64	2432
Total	100		

Table – 5. Pre-test scores of Mann-Whitney U test of the experimental and control groups

	Values
Mann-Whitney U	1343
Z	0.562878
Asymptotic Significance (2-tailed)	0.573518

Table - 6. Pre-test Mann-Whitney U-value, and Z-value of Educational Aspiration of students in the experimental and control groups at the upper primary level

Groups	Mean Ranks	N	Mann-Whitney U	Z - Value	Remark
Experiment	48.36	50	1343	0.562878	p>0.05
Control	52.64	50			

As is depicted in Tables 4,5 & 6, it is known that no significant difference was found in the educational aspirations of both the groups of upper primary level students even at 0.05 level of significance before the treatment. This indicates that the two groups were similar in terms of their educational aspirations, which is important because it suggests that any differences in learning outcomes between the groups can be attributed to the use of brain-based learning strategies and principles rather than differences in

pre-existing aspirations. This strengthens the validity of the study and suggests that the results obtained can be attributed to the treatment being studied rather than other factors. Therefore, the hypothesis made in this context, ‘there is no significant difference between the Educational Aspiration of students at the upper primary level in the experimental & control group before treatment’ is accepted.

Obj 3. To compare the Educational Aspiration of students at the upper primary level in the experimental and control group after treatment.

In the context of this objective, the researcher (after conducting the treatment) collected data on the educational aspirations of students in the

experimental and control groups of the upper primary level. The researcher calculated the mean, median, and standard deviation values of the educational aspirations for both groups. These values are presented in Table 7.

Table -7. Post-test scores of Educational Aspiration's mean, median, and standard deviation of students at the upper primary level in the experimental and control group

Groups	N	Mean	Median	Standard Deviation
Experimental	50	46.11	46	6.38
Control	50	39	38	4.19

It is known from the observation of the above table that after the treatment, the students in the experimental group were found an increased level of educational aspiration after the treatment, ranging from average realistic to above average realistic. Conversely, the students in the control group maintained their previous level of average realistic educational aspiration. Additionally, the median

scores of the experimental group students showed improvement, while there was no significant change in the median scores of educational aspiration for the control group students. The researcher used the Mann-Whitney U Test to compare the differences between these two groups post-treatment. Overall, these findings are summarized in Table 8.

Table - 8. Ranks of Educational Aspiration in experimental and control group after treatment

Groups	N	Mean rank	Sum of Ranks
Experimental	50	47.29	3364.5
Control	50	33.71	1645.5
Total	100		

Table - 9. Post-test scores of Mann-Whitney U test of the experimental and control groups

	Values
Mann-Whitney U	410.5
Z - Value	-2.36268
Asymptotic Significance (2-tailed)	1.981857

Table -10. Post-test Mann-Whitney U-value, and Z-value of Educational Aspiration of students in the experimental and control groups at upper primary level

Groups	Mean Ranks	N	Mann-Whitney U	Z - Value	Remark
Experiment	47.29	50	410.5	-2.36268	p<0.05
Control	33.71	50			

The above table indicates a significant difference in the educational aspirations of upper primary level students after receiving treatment, with a significance level of 0.05. This is supported by the Mann-Whitney U test value of 410.5 and a z-value that is significant at the 0.05 level. Table 9 further supports this observation by showing that the educational aspirations of students in the experimental group improved after learning through brain-based learning strategies, while no such changes were observed in the control group.

Based on these findings, it can be concluded that brain-based learning strategies used by teachers can make certain subject matter more clear, interesting, and effective for students, thereby

positively impacting their mindset towards those subjects. This positive impact can increase educational aspirations for that certain subjects and subject matter. Such efforts can also provide positive motivation and energy for students to learn, leading to positive impacts in other areas of learning. Therefore, it can be said that if teachers use brain-based learning strategies in their teaching, then there will be a possibility of a positive impact in other areas of learning along with the educational aspirations of the students in the future.

This conclusion is supported by research studies conducted by Ozden & Mehmet (2008), Bilal (2010), Varghese (2011), and Ramakrishnan (2019), which demonstrate that brain-based learning

strategies positively affect students' academic achievement, learning style, and interest in learning. Therefore, using brain-based learning strategies in teaching has the potential to positively impact students' educational aspirations and academic achievement. Therefore, the hypothesis made in the context of this objective 'There is no significant difference between Educational Aspiration of students at upper primary level in the experimental & control group after treatment' is rejected.

Obj 4. To study the effect of Brain-based Learning Strategies and conventional method on the Educational Aspiration of students at upper

primary level in the experimental and control group.

The objective of this study was to analyse the values of pre-test and post-test scores of both groups using various statistical techniques. To achieve this objective, the researcher utilized several statistical methods to obtain the necessary values. Tables 11, 12, and 13 display the obtained values for the control group. Specifically, Table 11 presents the mean, median, and standard deviation values of the educational aspirations of students at the upper primary level in the control group, for both the pre-test and post-test.

Table 11. Pre-test and Post-test mean, median, and standard deviation values of Educational Aspiration of students at the upper primary level in control group

	N	Mean	Median	Standard Deviation
Pre-Test	50	37.68	37	4.27
Post-Test	50	39.00	38	4.19

As is seen in table 11, that the pre-test and post-test scores for educational aspiration among upper primary level students in the control group were average. Hence, it can be inferred that the values of educational aspiration did not show significant

changes from pre-test to post-test in this group. To further investigate the similarity of the means between the two tests, the researcher conducted a Wilcoxon Sign Rank Test, and the results are presented in tables 12 and 13.

Table 12. Ranks of Educational Aspiration on the Pre-test and Post-test scores in control group

Post Test – Pre Test	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
Negative Ranks	7	15.57	109
Positive Ranks	43	27.12	1166
Ties	0		
Total	50		

Table - 13. Z-value of Educational Aspiration of students in control groups at upper primary level by Wilcoxon Sign Rank Test before and after treatment

	Post test Pre test
Z	2.102
P (2-tailed)	0.001

Based on the Wilcoxon Sign Rank Test results presented in Tables 12 and 13, it is evident that there is a significant difference in the pre-test and post-test scores of educational aspirations of the students in the control group. This difference may have been influenced by the researcher, who taught the same topics using two different teaching strategies for the experimental and control groups (brain-based learning strategies for the experimental group and traditional teaching methods for the control group). However, despite the observed difference, the mean,

median, and standard deviation values of both tests for the control group are quite similar, indicating that the difference found between the pre-test and post-test scores may not be significant, and could be due to chance factor. In order to examine the effect of brain-based learning strategies on the educational aspirations of the students in the experimental group, the researcher compared the pre-test and post-test values of educational aspirations among the students in the experimental group. These results have been presented in Table 14.

Table 14. Pre-test and Post-test mean, median, and standard deviation values of Educational Aspiration of students at the upper primary level in experimental group

	N	Mean	Median	Standard Deviation
Pre-Test	50	37.44	36	5.39
Post-Test	50	46.11	46	6.38

It is clear from the inspection of the above table/Upon reviewing the aforementioned table, it is evident that a noticeable difference exists between the pre-test and post-test values. Furthermore, the table indicates that the mean educational aspiration of the students prior to the test was average and realistic. However, following treatment, the mean educational aspiration of the students improved to an average realistic to above-average realistic level. The researcher utilized the Wilcoxon sign rank test to arrive at a conclusive determination. The results of this test are summarized in Tables 15 and 16.

Table 15. Ranks of Educational Aspiration on the Pre-test and Post-test scores in experimental group

Post Test – Pre Test		N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
	Negative Ranks	2	2.5	5
Positive Ranks	48	26.46	1328	
Ties	0			
Total	50			

Table - 16. Z-value of Educational Aspiration of students in experimental group at upper primary level by Wilcoxon Sign Rank Test before and after treatment

	Post test Pre test
Z	4.110
P (2-tailed)	0.001

Based on the observed results and the comparison of pre-test and post-test scores in the experimental group, it can be concluded that the use of brain-based learning strategies in teaching-learning activities has a positive and significant impact on the educational aspirations of students at the upper primary level. This finding is consistent with previous research studies conducted by Ozden & Mehmet (2008), Bilal (2010), Varghese (2011), and Ramakrishnan (2019). They also found similar results. Based on the results of Ramakrishnan's (2019) research, it is confirmed that brain-based learning is extremely helpful in enhancing the academic achievements and creativity of students. Similarly, Ozden & Gultekin (2008) found in their research that brain-based learning positively affects students' academic achievements and knowledge retention. According to Bilal's (2010) research study, it is evident that brain-based learning affects the academic achievement of students based on their learning style. Varghese (2011) studied the impact of brain-based learning on students' academic achievements, stress, and study habits in the context of biology and found that it has a positive influence on all these aspects.

The null hypothesis, which stated that there is no significant effect of brain-based teaching strategies and traditional methods on educational aspirations of students at the upper primary level in experimental and control groups after treatment, is rejected based on the observed significant difference in the pre-test and post-test scores of the experimental group at the 0.05 level of significance. This implies that the use of brain-based learning strategies can bring about meaningful changes in the behavior and academic activities of the student, which can have a positive impact on their

educational aspirations. While brain-based learning strategies have been shown to have a positive impact on students' educational aspirations, it's important to note that there is still ongoing research in this area. Some studies have found that the effectiveness of brain-based learning strategies may depend on a variety of factors, such as the age of the students, the subject being taught, and the specific strategies being used. However, it is generally agreed upon that brain-based learning approaches can help students to engage with the material in a more meaningful way and make connections between different concepts. This can lead to deeper learning and a greater understanding of the subject matter, which can, in turn, increase students' motivation and confidence.

Additionally, brain-based learning strategies often emphasize the use of collaborative and interactive activities, which can help students to develop their communication and teamwork skills. This can be beneficial not just in terms of their academic success but also in their personal and professional lives. Overall, while there is still more research to be done in this area, it seems that brain-based learning strategies have the potential to positively impact students' educational aspirations and overall well-being. This finding is consistent with previous research study conducted by Lazarides (2016), Parental expectations have a positive influence on the academic aspirations of students, and the organizational environment of the school (which is shaped by the activities of teachers) also positively affects the educational aspirations of students as found by Makkar (2010) in his research study. Vyas (2016) found in his research study, "Brain-based learning as a determinant of academic stress, test anxiety, and academic performance in

struggling learners," that students' academic stress, test anxiety, and academic performance are positively influenced towards a positive direction by brain-based learning strategies used by teachers. Therefore, this has a direct and indirect positive impact on students' interests, aspirations, and activity toward education. Brain-based learning is an approach that takes into account the neurological processes involved in learning. By understanding how the brain works, teachers can create learning environments and experiences that are more effective for their students. This can lead to improved learning outcomes and increased educational aspirations. When teachers use brain-based teaching strategies, they can help students develop logical thinking skills and a deeper understanding of complex topics. This is because the brain is able to more easily process and interpret abstract information when it is presented in a way that is aligned with its natural processes.

In addition, brain-based learning can help students maintain their mental stability and emotional well-being, which is essential for their success in the classroom and beyond. By understanding how the brain responds to stress and anxiety, teachers can create supportive learning environments that promote positive emotional experiences and reduce the risk of negative outcomes. Overall, when teachers use brain-based teaching strategies, they can help their students achieve their educational aspirations in the context of various dimensions of educational aspirations (Family support, pupil's view, pupil's effort, and reality of aspired goal) by providing them with the tools and resources they need to succeed. This includes creating engaging and stimulating learning environments, using effective teaching techniques, and providing support and guidance when needed. Therefore, researcher can able to said that teachers should use brain-based teaching strategies in their teaching work, as it has a direct impact on the educational aspirations of their students. By doing so, teachers can help their students to develop the skills and knowledge they need to succeed in life, both academically and beyond.

12. Finding and Conclusion

The results of this research show that the use of brain-based learning strategies by teachers in their teaching has a positive impact on the educational aspirations of students. Therefore, it can be said that in order to enhance the educational aspirations of students, teachers should use brain-based learning strategies in their teaching. This is because when educational aspirations are high, there is an increased likelihood that the level of education in the country will also rise, which can be seen to have an impact on various activities of students and society. Confirmation of this fact is also based on

research studies conducted by Ozden & Mehmet (2008), Bilal (2010), Varghese (2011), and Ramakrishnan (2019) in which brain-based learning structures positively affect students' academic achievement, behavior, knowledge retention, learning style, creativity, academic performance, academic stress, etc. Rekha (2012) also developed a program in the context of brain-based learning strategies views. This program aimed to positively impact students' academic behaviors and actions, with the goal of enhancing their performance in various aspects.

In addition, educational aspirations also guide vocational aspirations, and when a student's vocational aspirations are high, there is a greater possibility of economic and social development in our country in the context of various professions. Therefore, keeping in mind the fact that "the development of the country takes place in the classrooms of the country," teachers should use brain-based learning strategies in their teaching to enhance the educational aspirations of students. This will make their teaching more effective, and students will be able to contribute fully to various activities during their education, while understanding the subject matter in a practical way.

13. Suggestions

For policymaker - Policymakers should ensure that teachers at every level of education are made aware of the principles and strategies of brain-based learning through various workshops, seminars, conferences, and other training programs. Additionally, practical information related to these concepts should also be provided to teachers so that they can make meaningful use of them in their classrooms.

For Principal/institutional authority - The principal or institutional authority of the school should organize various workshops, seminars, conferences, and training programs related to providing knowledge about brain-based learning principles and strategies to teachers in their school. This will keep the teachers informed about the strategies from time to time. Additionally, they would be able to update their teaching methods and techniques based on brain-based learning according to changing social situations and circumstances. The principals should provide teachers with high-quality books (on various subjects), computer and internet facilities, teaching aids, an appropriate environment for learning, etc. in their school premises. Furthermore, principals should provide necessary arrangements for teachers to teach through various strategies, methods, techniques etc of brain-based learning in each classroom.

For teachers – Teachers should use brain-based learning strategies in their teaching to make their own teaching more effective. This can positively

impact students' educational aspirations, educational achievements, learning outcomes, and other psychological factors, as well as provide teachers with personal satisfaction, resulting in higher performance levels in their schools. With the help of BBL (Brain-Based Learning), teachers can easily achieve their teaching objectives. In this regard, teachers should analyze each topic of their subject based on the principles of brain-based learning, and use BBL strategies to make teaching and subject matter more effective. Subsequently, teachers should continue to use various methods under BBL with students to teach all these subject matters effectively in every class, and transform the teaching activities in the classroom into an active and child-centred learning process.

For students - Through BBL, students are able to understand the subject matter taught in a practical way and retain it for a longer period of time, while also being able to use it in the future. Therefore, students should also engage in studying by using brain-based learning principles. They should provide full support to the different teaching methods and techniques used in the classroom by teachers for various concepts. They should also show active participation in these methods, so that an environment is created in the classroom where the relationship between the subject matter, teacher and students becomes very strong, and it can be easily used in any situation in the future. In addition, students should also show their creativity during the teaching and learning process by using BBL, and give various innovative ideas to the teachers.

For Parents - In this context, parents should also contact teachers to learn various teaching-learning methods for effective teaching and use them when teaching their children at home. Additionally, based on these teaching methods, parents can provide various facilities to their children at home, so that their understanding and educational aspirations can take a positive shape in the future. These educational aspirations also influence students' vocational aspirations. Therefore, if the teaching-learning process is effective, children will be able to easily determine their future in today's competitive society. Parents should provide various facilities to their children such as various subject-related materials, various games, books, household items for experimental, and practical use of theoretical knowledge, etc.

For Society - In the context of brain-based learning, social workers and social activists who contribute to various activities in society should use brain-based learning in the context of various approaches of mass media to create various online teaching-learning content that can have a positive impact on the personalities of future creators of society. Additionally, books, games, experimental

equipment, and other resources related to various subjects should be made available to society according to different levels of education, so that all children in society can benefit from them.

Therefore, based on the results of this study, it is known that brain-based learning strategies are highly effective in teaching, as students actively show their participation, resulting in a highly effective learning process. Additionally, brain-based learning strategies increase student participation and interest in educational activities, positively impacting their educational aspirations. The relationship between these educational aspirations and student learning is evident in every activity related to their learning. So, all teachers should be concerned about the student's educational aspirations. It is more clear when brain-based learning strategies are used in teaching and learning activities, various activities related to educational aspirations of students are also positively influenced, and students exhibit positive behavior toward learning. Based on this research study, it can be said that teachers should use brain-based learning strategies in their teaching-learning process to increase students' educational aspirations and make the learning process more meaningful.

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